

A Note on Fractional Simpson-like Type Inequality for Functions whose Second Derivatives are of Bounded Variation

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Abstract

In this study, a Simpson-type equality for the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral is established. Using this equality, several fractional Simpson-type inequalities are proved for functions whose second derivatives are of bounded variation.

Keywords: Fractional integrals, Simpson-type inequality, bounded variation

1 Introduction

Fractional calculus has become an essential tool in the analysis of various mathematical models due to its ability to capture memory and hereditary properties. In particular, fractional integral inequalities play a significant role in establishing bounds and estimating errors in numerical approximation methods. Among these, Simpson-type inequalities provide effective estimates for integrals and have recently been extended to the fractional setting. Motivated by these developments, we investigate a Simpson-type equality involving the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral. Based on this equality, we derive several fractional Simpson-like inequalities for functions whose second derivatives are of bounded variation.

Now, let us give the definition of a function of bounded variation and introduce the basic concepts of fractional calculus that will be needed in subsequent analysis.

Definition 1.1. Let $P : a = x_0 < x_1 < \dots < x_n = b$ be any partition of $[a, b]$ and let $\Delta F(x_i) = F(x_{i+1}) - F(x_i)$. Then F is said to be of bounded variation if the sum

$$\sum_{i=1}^n |\Delta F(x_i)|$$

is bounded for all such partitions.

Let F be of bounded variation on $[a, b]$, and $\sum \Delta F(P)$ denotes the sum $\sum_{i=1}^n |\Delta F(x_i)|$ corresponding to the partition P of $[a, b]$. The number

$$V_a^b(F) := \sup \left\{ \sum \Delta F(P) : P \in (P[a, b]) \right\}$$

is called the total variation of F on $[a, b]$. Here $P([a, b])$ denotes the family of partitions of $[a, b]$.

Definition 1.2. (See [4, 7]) If $f \in L_1[a, b]$ is a function, then the integrals $I_{a+}^\alpha f(x)$ and $I_{b-}^\alpha f(x)$ of order $\alpha > 0$ are defined by

$$I_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$I_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b,$$

respectively. These integrals are called Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals in the literature. Here, Γ is the Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{\alpha-1} du.$$

Fractional integral inequalities and their applications have been established using the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral. For example, Sarikaya and colleagues have established some Simpson-like inequalities for functions with convex second derivatives [8]. Hezenci and Budak have also proven some fractional Simpson-like inequalities for functions with convex third derivatives in absolute values [5]. Furthermore, some fractional Simpson-like inequalities for functions with convex second derivatives in absolute values have been proven in [6]. For more information on various properties of Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals and various fractional integral operators, the reader is referred to [3, 2, 1].

The aim of this paper is to establish a new Simpson-like equation based on the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral and, using this equation, to obtain various fractional Simpson-like inequalities for functions with bounded variations in second derivatives. The overall design of this paper consists of four sections, including the introduction. A new Simpson-type equation, which serves as the main tool of the study, is established in Section 2. In Section 3, various fractional Simpson-type inequalities are derived using the equation obtained in Section 2. Finally, in Section 4, the results are discussed.

2 A New and Essential Equality

In this section, we derive a key integral identity that forms the foundation for the principal results presented in this paper.

Lemma 2.1. Let $F : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a three times differentiable function on $[a, b]$ such that

$F'''L \in [a, b]$. Then, the following equality holds

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \left[F(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha)F\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + F(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha - F(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha + F(b) \right] \\ &= \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \int_a^b p(x) d(F''(x)), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$p(x) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^2, & a < x \leq \frac{a+b}{2}, \\ \left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2}, & \frac{a+b}{2} < x < b. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \int_a^b p(x) d(F''(x)) &= \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^2 \right] d(F''(x)) \\ &+ \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \left[\left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} \right] d(F''(x)) \end{aligned}$$

By applying integration by parts, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^2 \right] d(F''(x)) \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^2 \right] F''(x) \Big|_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \\ &- \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} (\alpha+2)(x-a)^{\alpha+1} - \frac{8}{(b-a)^2}(x-a) \right] d(F'(x)) \\ &= - \left[\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} (\alpha+2)(x-a)^{\alpha+1} - \frac{8}{(b-a)^2}(x-a) \right] F'(x) \Big|_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \\ &+ \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} (\alpha+2)(\alpha+1)(x-a)^\alpha - \frac{8}{(b-a)^2} \right] d(F(x)) \\ &= \left[\frac{4}{b-a} - \frac{2(\alpha+2)}{b-a} \right] F' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + \left[(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2) \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} (x-a)^\alpha - \frac{8}{(b-a)^2} \right] F(x) \Big|_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \\ &- \frac{\alpha(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)2^{\alpha+2}\Gamma(\alpha)}{(b-a)^{\alpha+2}} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} (x-a)^\alpha F(x) dx \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} I_2 &= \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \left[\left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} \right] d(F''(x)) \\ &= \left[\frac{2(\alpha+2)}{b-a} - \frac{4}{b-a} \right] F' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + \left[\frac{8}{(b-a)^2} - (\alpha+1)(\alpha+2) \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} (b-x)^\alpha \right] F(x) \Big|_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \\ &- \frac{\alpha(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)2^{\alpha+2}\Gamma(\alpha)}{(b-a)^{\alpha+2}} \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b (b-x)^\alpha F(x) dx \end{aligned}$$

If we add I_1 and I_2 , we obtain the following equation

$$I_1 + I_2 = 8 \left[\frac{(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)}{(b - a)^2} - \frac{2}{(b - a)^2} \right] F \left(\frac{a + b}{2} \right) + \frac{8}{(b - a)^2} [F(a) + F(b)] - \frac{\alpha(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)2^{\alpha+2}\Gamma(\alpha)}{(b - a)^{\alpha+2}} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha F(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha F(b) \right]$$

Thus the proof is completed. □

3 Simpson-Like Inequalities

Theorem 3.1. Let $F : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be such that F'' is a continuous function of bounded variation on $[a, b]$. Then we have the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left[F(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha)F \left(\frac{a + b}{2} \right) + F(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(b - a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha F(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha F(b) \right] \right| \leq \frac{\alpha 2^{2/\alpha-3}(b - a)^2}{(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)^{2/\alpha+2}} \bigvee_a^b(F'').$$

Proof. From the equality (1), we can write

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left[F(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha)F \left(\frac{a + b}{2} \right) + F(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(b - a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha F(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha F(b) \right] \right| \\ &= \frac{(b - a)^2}{8(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left| \int_a^b p(x) d(F''(x)) \right| \\ &= \frac{1}{2(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \\ & \times \left| \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{2}{b - a} \right)^\alpha (x - a)^{\alpha+2} - (x - a)^2 \right] d(F''(x)) + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \left[(b - x)^2 - \left(\frac{2}{b - a} \right)^\alpha (b - x)^{\alpha+2} \right] d(F''(x)) \right| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left| \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{2}{b - a} \right)^\alpha (x - a)^{\alpha+2} - (x - a)^2 \right] d(F''(x)) \right| \\ &+ \frac{1}{2(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \left[(b - x)^2 - \left(\frac{2}{b - a} \right)^\alpha (b - x)^{\alpha+2} \right] d(F''(x)) \right| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left\{ \sup_{x \in [a, \frac{a+b}{2}]} \left| \left(\frac{2}{b - a} \right)^\alpha (x - a)^{\alpha+2} - (x - a)^2 \right| \bigvee_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}}(F'') \right. \\ & \left. + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+b}{2}, b]} \left| (b - x)^2 - \left(\frac{2}{b - a} \right)^\alpha (b - x)^{\alpha+2} \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b(F'') \right\} \\ &\leq \frac{\alpha 2^{2/\alpha-3}(b - a)^2}{(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)^{2/\alpha+2}} \bigvee_a^b(F'') \end{aligned}$$

Thus the proof is completed. □

Corollary 3.1. If we choose $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 3.1, then the following Simpson type inequality

holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[F(a) + 4F\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + F(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b F(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{324} \mathcal{V}_a^b(F'').$$

4 Conclusions

In this study, a new Simpson-type equation is derived in the framework of the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral, and various fractional Simpson-like inequalities are derived using this equation for functions whose second derivatives have a bounded total variation. The results generalize the classical Simpson inequality to the fractional integral context and provide new evaluations valid for a broader class of functions. The findings here are expected to provide a foundation for applications of fractional calculus associated with fractional integral operators.

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